

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID-ANTIVIRAL ACTIVITY by qPCR_VIRUCIDAL CMP
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Version:	01	
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1. Goal and Area of Application

When evaluating the antiviral effect of a compound, assessing cellular toxicity in the target cell line is an essential prerequisite (see dedicated SOP). The highest dose allowing > 90 % cell viability is the first tested dose in antiviral assay. Quantifying viruses in the supernatants of infected cell cultures enables the evaluation of the antiviral efficacy of compounds. Vero E6 cell line is used for SARS-CoV-2 infection and Huh7 cell line for WNV and CHIKV infection.

2. Definitions and Abbreviations

CHIKV	Chikungunya virus
WNV	West Nile virus
CMPs	Compounds
qPCR	quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction
RT-PCR	Retrotranscription followed by Polymerase Chain Reaction
DMSO	Dimethylsulfoxide

3. Method

3.1 General

This SOP describes the evaluation of antiviral efficacy of virucidal compounds by quantitative Polymerase Chain Reaction that measures the amount of viral RNA in the supernatant of infected cells. Virucidal compounds act directly on the virus and are pre-incubated with viruses before cell infection. This technique implies cell infection with a complete virus and therefore requires a BSL-3 facility.

The antiviral efficacy of a compound is measured by incubating a constant dose of virus with serial dilutions of the compound. Target cells are then exposed to the virus/compound mixture. Supernatant from SARS-CoV-2 infected VeroE6 cells and from CHIKV or WNV infected Huh7 cells is harvested 2 days after infection. After viral RNA extraction, a one-step quantitative RT-PCR (Taqman technology) is performed to determine the % of inhibition by the relative reduction of target RNA in treated sample as compared to untreated infected control.

Note : For Light-sensitive compounds, tests have to be performed in dark condition

3.2 Information for consommables / chemicals /equipment

Product name	Supplier	Ordering n°
DMEM High Glucose	Gibco	61965059
Fetal Bovine Serum	e.g. Gibco	e.g. 10270-106
Penicillin/Streptomycin	Gibco	15140
DMSO	Sigma	472301
Favipiravir	MCE	HY-14768

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Sofosbuvir	Clinisciences	HY-15005
Remdesivir	MCE	HY-104077
Sterile 96 well culture plate, flat bottom (polystyrene)	e.g. Dutscher	e.g. 353072
Huh7 cells LOT. 07162024	JCRB Cell Bank.	JCRB0403
VeroE6 cells	Gift from Arbovirus CNR	
SARS-CoV-2 viral stock	In house viral stocks	
WNV viral stock	In house viral stocks	Austria L2 lineage
CHIKV viral stock	In house viral stocks	ECISA strain P2
Qiamp viral RNA minikit	Qiagen	52906
Investigational compounds		

EQUIPMENT		
Superscript TM III Platinum® One-Step qRT-PCR	Invitrogen	11732-08
Thermocycler	Roche	Light cycler 480
3D rotative platform	e.g. FISHERBRAND	e.g. 888861046

3.3 Procedure

3.3.1 Cell seeding + control drug treatment (DAY 0)

- Cells are seeded in flat bottom 96-well plates, at a defined density specific to each cell line early in the morning

- ◆ 10,000 cells / well for VeroE6 cells
- ◆ 8,000 cells / well for Huh7 cells

- After 6 hours incubation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ to allow proper adhesion and stabilization, control wells are treated with a control drug that inhibit nearly 100% of viral infection

* 10 µM of Remdesivir for SARS-CoV-2

* 50 µM of Sofosbuvir for WNV

* 100 µM of Favipiravir for CHIKV

- Plates are then incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ for 16h

3.3.2 Virus + compound pre-incubation (DAY 1)

Note: For compounds sensitive to light, tests have to be performed IN DARK CONDITION

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- First the initial stock solutions of compounds are diluted to the double of the highest non-toxic concentration in the appropriate medium (including DMSO if needed for compound solubility) to account for the further 2-fold dilution due to mixing with the virus.
- Then serial dilutions with a 2-fold dilution ratio are carried out in the appropriate medium.
- For each tested viruses, a viral solution is prepared in DMEM 0% FCS for a final MOI 0.01
- Finally, the viral solutions are mixed 1:1 with the compounds' dilutions to obtain the desired range of concentrations.
- A 1:1 mix of DMEM 0% FCS and the CMPs dilutions will be used as non-infected, treated control.
- The mixes are incubated 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂

3.3.3 Viral stocks titration (DAY 1)

- During (Virus + compound pre-incubation), the viral stocks are titrated
- Serial 10-fold dilutions of the viral stocks are made in DMEM 0% FCS
 - VeroE6 cells are infected with the dilutions from 10⁻² to 10⁻⁶ (for SARS-CoV-2 strains titration) or from 10⁻² to 10⁻⁹ (for WNV and CHIKV stocks) (8 replicate/dilution)
 - The plates are incubated 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂
 - Medium is renewed with DMEM 2% FCS and plates are incubated for 4-5 days at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂

3.3.4 Cells infection (DAY 1)

- Vero E6 cells (for SARS-CoV-2 studies) or Huh7 cells (for CHIKV and WNV studies) are treated with the dilutions of viruses + CMP in duplicate wells
- The plates were incubated 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂
- Medium is renewed with DMEM 2% FCS
- Control wells previously treated are also infected for 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂
- Medium is then replaced by DMEM 2% FCS with control drug (10 µM of Remdesivir for SARS-CoV-2; 50 µM of Sofosbuvir for WNV; 100 µM of Favipiravir for CHIKV)
- The non-treated control is also infected for 1h under agitation at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂. Medium is then replaced by DMEM 2% FCS
- Non-infected control cells are treated with the CMP diluted with DMEM 0% FCS

Plates are incubated at 37°C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂ for 2 days to measure virus inhibition, and for 4-5 days to verify the virus titre.

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3.3.5 Supernatant harvesting (DAY 3)

For each experimental well: 140 µL of culture supernatant is collected and mixed with 560 µL of AVL buffer (from Qiagen viral RNA extraction kit) in Eppendorf tubes.

After 10 minutes incubation at room temperature, the samples can be moved out of the level 3 biosafety laboratory for viral RNA extraction and RT-qPCR analysis

3.3.6 Viral RNA extraction and quantitative RT-PCR analysis (Taqman technology)

Viral RNA is extracted from cell culture supernatant using the commercial kit Qiampr viral RNA minikit (QIAGEN) following the recommendation from the provider. The final elution volume is 60 µL. Extracted RNA can be stored at -20°C (short time storage) or -80°C (long time storage) before qRT-PCR.

The viral load is determined by qRT-PCR using the primers and probe corresponding to each viruses.

Primers and Probe

*SARS-CoV-2 (107pb RdRp gene / nCoV_IP4)

nCoV_IP4-14059Fw GGTAAGTGGTATGATTTTCG 19

nCoV_IP4-14146Rv CTGGTCAAGGTTAATATAGG 20 107 bp 1

nCoV_IP4-14084 Probe(+) TCATACAAACCACGCCAGG [5']Fam [3']BHQ-1

*CHIKV (208bp in E1 structural protein region)

R-CHIK CCAAATTGTCCYGGTCTTCCT 10554–10574

F-CHIK AAGCTYCGCGTCCTTTACCAAG 10366–10387

P-CHIK bCCAATGTCYTCMGCCTGGACACCTTc 10465–10490

*WNV (92bp in 3' non coding region)

WN10533-10552: WN-3NC-F (AAG TTG AGT AGA CGG TGC TG)

WN10625-10606: WN-3NC-R (AGA CGG TTC TGA GGG CTT AC)

Probe WN10560-10579: (CTC AAC CCC AGG AGG ACT GG) labeled with (FAM) at 5'-end and a non-fluorescent reagent, Blackhole, at 3'-end

Reaction mixes and Light cycler LC480 settings

* SARS-CoV-2

	Vol (µl)	[final]
H2O PPI	3.6	
Reaction mix 2X	12.50	3 mM Mg
MgCl ₂	0.4	0.8 mM Mg
Forward Primer (10µM)	1	0.4 µM
Reverse Primer (10µM)	1	0.4 µM

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Probe (10µM)	0.5	0.2 µM
SuperscriptIII RT/Platinum Taq Mix	1	
Final Volume	20.00	

+ Add 5µL extracted viral RNA

LC480 settings

Reverse transcription 55°C 1200sec
Amplification (50x) 95°C 15 sec
58°C 30 sec (acq single)

* CHIKV

	Vol (µl)	[final]
H2O PPI	4	
Reaction mix 2X	12.50	3 mM Mg
Forward Primer (10µM)	1	0.4 µM
Reverse Primer (10µM)	1	0.4 µM
Probe (10µM)	0.5	0.2 µM
SuperscriptIII RT/Platinum Taq Mix	1	
Final Volume	20.00	

+ Add 5µL extracted viral RNA

LC480 settings

Reverse transcription 50°C 900sec
Denaturation 95°C 120 sec
Amplification (40x) 95°C 15 sec
55°C 15sec
60°C 30sec -> (acq single)

* WNV

	Vol (µl)	[final]
H2O PPI	4,625	
Reaction mix 2X	12.50	3 mM Mg
Forward Primer (10µM)	0,75	0.3 µM
Reverse Primer (10µM)	0,75	0.3 µM
Probe (10µM)	0.375	0.15 µM
SuperscriptIII RT/Platinum Taq Mix	1	
Final Volume	20.00	

+ Add 5µL extracted viral RNA

LC480 settings

Reverse transcription 50°C 900sec
Denaturation 95°C 120 sec

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Amplification (40x) 95°C 15 sec
 49°C WN 15sec
 60°C 30sec -> (acq single)

3.3.7 CPE evaluation for Viral stock titration (DAY 4-5)

Viral stocks are titrated by counting the number of wells showing a cytopathic effect for each dilution and using the Spearman and Kärber algorithm.

3.3.8 Data analysis and interpretation

1. Viral stock titer conformity evaluated by TCID50

The expected viral stock titer (used to calculate the volumes needed for viral suspension) and the read viral stock titer (evaluated during the experiment) should not differ by more than half a log. Otherwise the experiment is invalidated.

2. % of viral inhibition analysis

The % of inhibition is determined by the relative reduction of target RNA in treated sample as compared to untreated infected control based on Ct obtained by qRT-PCR.

$$\Delta Ct = Ct \text{ control} - Ct \text{ treated}$$

$$\% \text{ inhibition} = (1 - 2^{-\Delta Ct}) \times 100$$

The mean value of the 2 technical replicates is calculated. Viral replication in the positive control condition (non treated cells) is set to 100% and used for normalization.

Note: The % of inhibition should be closed to 100% with control drugs to validate the experiment.

Statistical analyses and IC₅₀ calculations on GraphPad Prism.

On Graphpad Prism, the mean and SEM % of viral replication for each tested doses are plotted. The IC₅₀ is calculated using XY Analysis -> non linear regression (curve fit) [Inhibitor] vs. response (three parameters)

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IC50 (µM) 0.09368

4. Further applicable documents

QIAamp® Viral RNA Mini Handbook